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Optimizing interfaces and inner faculty discussions: Toward a transparent design of engineering curricula

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INTRODUCTION

The modularisation of study programmes and the increase of potential contents of those leads to a growing number of selection choices and an increasing flexibility in the individual curriculum design. Furthermore, the Lisbon Recognition Convention eases the mobility of students during their studies. This allows the students to develop a more specific profile of competences. Therefore, an appropriate description of the learning outcomes of the individual modules and an increase in the transparency of the interfaces revealing the interconnection between the different modules is crucial for ensuring consistent personal curricula and the continuous acquisition of competencies.

Currently, learning outcomes are usually described in continuous texts using Bloom's taxonomy [1] or its revised version by Anderson and Krathwohl [2]. Although these taxonomies and the depicted way for describing learning outcomes is commonly accepted, there are problems regarding a clear description of the acquired competences in engineering sciences. Furthermore, the current approach impedes the evaluation of module interfaces in a database.

In order to overcome these issues, we developed a revised taxonomy and elaborated a strategy which introduces a tabular description of learning outcomes [3]. Moreover, we created a tool for the analysis of module interfaces, where module interfaces are gathered, visualised, and analysed in an interactive web-based content management system [4].

Chapter 1 summarizes theoretical considerations including the introduction of the revised taxonomy and an appropriate concept for describing learning outcomes. Furthermore, it presents a theoretical approach for the evaluation of module interfaces and explains the procedure for the detection of conflicts at module interfaces. Chapter 2 deals with the practical realization of an interactive web-based content management system for the analysis of module interfaces for an engineering study programme. It presents the user interfaces for students and teachers. Chapter 3 summarizes the resulting opportunities and chances and gives an outlook on further extensions. A final recap is given in Chapter 4.

1 THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This section introduces a revised taxonomy for engineering sciences as well as a new approach for the description of learning outcomes. It discusses how module interfaces can be evaluated, when learning outcomes are formulated by means of the suggested taxonomy.

1.1 Revised taxonomy for engineering sciences

Although the taxonomies of Bloom and Anderson and Krathwohl are commonly accepted, the order of the qualification levels and the coarseness of the classification lead to problems regarding a clear description of the acquired competences in engineering sciences. Thus, we extended Anderson's and Krathwohl's revision of Bloom's taxonomy for the explicit application to engineering studies [3].

We made use of the learning model of Hoffmann [5] as well as concepts of 4ING [6], the EQF [7], and the DQR [8]. Accordingly, we decided to express the level of qualification via a breakdown into quantified levels of **knowledge** (know what), **skills** (know how), and **competences** (know why). *Table 1* shows the resulting taxonomy.

Table 1: Revised taxonomy for engineering sciences

	0	1	2	3	4
Knowledge (Know what)	no memory	lookup-knowledge	learnt by heart	learnt and understood	analysis and evaluation
Skills (Know how)	no skills	passive scheme	active scheme	experienced processing	
Competences (Know why)	Level of compliance with the following wording: The students can put the respective topic comprising assigned knowledge and skills in a superordinate context. Combining different topics, they are available for discussions and can structure complex novel tasks using their stock of knowledge and skills, can identify contained gaps and plan their proceeding.				
	no compliance	low compliance	moderate compliance	high compliance	highest compliance

Corresponding to the definitions of 4ING, **knowledge** is “learnt, retrievable information on facts, the context, to which facts are associated, and the rules interrelating facts to contexts” [9]. **Skills** depicts “an ability that has been acquired by training, and that makes use of the implicit memory, to apply knowledge to standard situations, and to use know-how to complete standard tasks, and to solve standard problems” [9]. Finally, **competences** are “the proven ability to autonomously recognize interrelations between facts and the contexts to which they are linked, to apply this ability to systematically develop new methods, and, if indicated, to apply them to changed situations” [9].

1.2 New approach for describing learning outcomes

Besides the new taxonomy, we introduced a tabular description of learning outcomes replacing continuous texts. In order to set an appropriate level of aggregation, we formulate learning outcomes by rating module contents using the qualification levels provided by the new taxonomy.

Table 2: Exemplary classification of learning outcomes

Learning contents	Achieved learning outcomes		
	Knowledge	Skills	Competences
Equilibrium of forces	4	3	4
Multiaxial stress states	3	2	2

Table 2 exemplarily contains two learning outcomes, which are formulated using the presented approach. Apart from an appropriate and clear description of learning outcomes, which is suitable for engineering sciences, this approach enables the evaluation of module interfaces in a database.

1.3 Definition and analysis of module interfaces

Using the suggested concept, learning outcomes can be catalogued systematically. As a result, module interfaces can be defined and evaluated. Figure 1 depicts the structure of the interfaces of a certain module topic and the related learning outcome A. Besides an interface to one or more base topics and the related learning outcomes B, the module topic has interfaces to one or more subsequent topics and the related learning outcomes C.

Fig. 1: Structure of a module interface

In order to generate interfaces between different module topics, it is necessary to define the required input and achieved output (learning outcome) related to each topic. As the description of learning outcomes represents the acquired output, teachers further need to define the required input of each module. Therefore, they need to check on which base topics they can build on and to define the required level of qualification in the selected base topics. Connections between module topics and subsequent topics are generated when module topics are defined as an input for the subsequent topics.

As a result, module interfaces can be evaluated and level conflicts can be detected. The evaluation can either take place Top-Down or Bottom-Up. Doing a Top-Down analysis of module interfaces, teachers examine, whether the chosen base topics deliver learning outcomes on the level required for their respective module topics. In a Bottom-Up analysis, however, they check, whether the achieved levels of qualification in their own module topic matches the level required for a subsequent topic. In order to detect time conflicts, teachers further need to define the sequence of the modules in the curriculum and the order of the different topics within a module.

2 PRACTICAL REALIZATION

This section describes the technical implementation of the web-based content management system developed for the analysis of module interfaces for an engineering study programmes. It shows the structure and content of the user interfaces for students and teachers.

2.1 Technical implementation

In order to display and evaluate module interfaces and consequently the structure of a study programme, an efficient technical implementation is required. As no satisfying solution was available, we developed a web-based content management system and have filled it with data from two bachelor programmes in engineering sciences. All

necessary information concerning module contents and interfaces is gathered in a MySQL-database. Metadata on courses, like contact information of teachers, can automatically be imported from the campus management system of the university. Using a PHP-based web-interface, teachers can manage their data and define interfaces efficiently. Furthermore, we designed a user interface for students which visualizes the interconnection between the different modules.

2.2 User interface for students

As schematically shown in *Table 3*, the student-interface gives information on the learning outcomes of the single modules and on the required input. Furthermore, modules which require the acquired learning outcomes as input are named.

Table 3: Extract from student-interface

Module: <i>Technical Mechanics I</i>																
Base topics	Module topics	Subsequent topics														
<i>Advanced Mathematics I</i> - Matrix calculus, determinants <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Knowledge</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Skills</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </table> <i>Technical Mechanics I</i> - Forces and moments <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Knowledge</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Skills</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </table>	Knowledge	3	Skills	2	Knowledge	3	Skills	2	Equilibrium of forces <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Knowledge</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Skills</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Competences</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </table>	Knowledge	4	Skills	3	Competences	4	<i>Hydromechanics</i> - Hydrostatics <i>Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering Basic Module</i> - Slope stability <i>Technical Mechanics II</i> - Bending of beams - Shear stresses due to bending - Stability of elastic systems
Knowledge	3															
Skills	2															
Knowledge	3															
Skills	2															
Knowledge	4															
Skills	3															
Competences	4															

Table 3 visualises some interfaces of the module *Technical Mechanics I*, which is one of the principal core modules of Civil Engineering. Several consecutive modules rely on the related learning outcomes. One of the contained topics is *equilibrium of forces*; the related levels of qualification are listed. The two base topics are *matrix calculus, determinants* handled in the module *Advanced Mathematics I* and *forces and moments* dealt with in *Technical Mechanics I*. The required levels of qualification in the base topics, which are needed for *equilibrium of forces*, are named. The topic itself is related to a number of subsequent topics building on the archived learning outcomes, being for example the topic *Hydrostatics* handled in the module *Hydromechanics*.

2.3 User interface for teachers

Using the teacher interface, teachers can define the learning outcomes and required input of their modules and consequently generate interfaces between different modules. Furthermore, a tool for the evaluation of conflicts at module interfaces is available. This tool allows teachers to easily assess possible conflicts for their module topics. *Table 4* exemplarily shows conflicts related to the topic *multiaxial stress states*. Listing the acquired knowledge and skills of the base topic as well as the knowledge

and skills required by the subsequent topic, the tool provides both, a Top-Down analysis (first and second conflict) and Bottom-Up analysis (third conflict). Besides level conflicts, which are marked red, the tool can give indications on time conflicts, which are marked yellow.

Table 4: Extract from tool for the evaluation of conflicts at module interfaces

Base topic	Subsequent topic	Knowledge		Skills	
		taught	required	taught	required
Top-Down					
Equilibrium of forces (Technical Mechanics I)	Multiaxial stress states	4	3	3	3
Vector calculus and analytic geometry (Advanced Mathematics I)	Multiaxial stress states	4	3	3	1
Bottom -Up					
Multiaxial stress states	Procedure elastic-elastic (Metal Structures Basic Module)	3	3	2	3

3 BENEFITS AND FUTURE EXTENSIONS

Based on the findings depicted above, various benefits and chances arise, which are summarized in this section. Furthermore, an outlook on possible extensions is given.

3.1 Benefits of the revised taxonomy

The revised taxonomy in conjunction with a tabular representation facilitates the process for the description of learning outcomes. Compared to the current approach, qualification levels no longer have to be translated into appropriate verbal formulations and the level of aggregation of learning outcomes matches the one of the module contents. As the proposed taxonomy holds a finer scaling, the assignment of qualification levels is facilitated.

Besides enabling the evaluation of module interfaces, the proposed concept for describing learning outcomes facilitates important processes like competence oriented examination and the recognition of credits. Adapting questions to the aspired qualification level is facilitated when using the new approach for the description of learning outcomes. Having drafted an exam task, it is easy to check, whether the levels of knowledge, skills, and competences required for solving the problem match the aspired levels. Additionally, the new approach simplifies the recognition of credits, which becomes more important due to the increasing mobility of students. The comparison of the learning outcomes of different modules is facilitated when learning outcomes are described in tabular form, since this kind of description is more explicit and usually uses a lower level of aggregation. A prerequisite for a fair proceeding is, more than ever, a conscientious, realistic assignment of levels of qualification.

3.2 Benefits due to the tool for the evaluation

Having detailed information about the module interfaces and consequently the required input and acquired output of the single modules, students are supported in their individual curriculum design. Consistent personal curricula and a continuous acquisition of competences are ensured. Furthermore, information about module interfaces motivates students to practice for modules without obvious practical relevance when knowing in which modules the acquired competences are required.

Besides the benefits for students, the evaluation of module interfaces holds also opportunities for teachers. As the tool enables the detection of conflicts between learning outcomes of different modules, it enhances inner faculty discussions concerning the curriculum design. Based on the information provided by the tool, teachers can improve the adjustment of the single modules by adapting their content, the order of the topics as well as the sequence of the modules in the curriculum.

3.3 Outlook

The developed tool for the evaluation of module interfaces has even further potential. For example, a feature which automatically suggests appropriate modules to the students could be added based on personal user accounts containing the profile of competences which the students aspire to. Another possible extension is a feature for a further simplification of competence oriented examination. Based on the levels of knowledge, skills, and competences assigned to a module topic, the feature could propose suitable examination formats. In order to ensure the reliability of the gathered learning outcomes, a feedback loop based on a self-assessment of the students could be added. Thereby it could be checked, whether the learning outcomes estimated by the teachers match the qualification levels achieved by the students.

4 SUMMARY

The modularisation of study programmes, the increasing flexibility in the individual curriculum design, and the growing mobility leads to the requirement of an appropriate description of learning outcomes and an increasing transparency in the curriculum. In order to meet these needs, we introduced a revised taxonomy allowing for a tabular and precise representation of learning outcomes. Based on the taxonomy, this paper presents a tool for the evaluation of module interfaces. The web-based system provides a unique transparency of study programmes to students and teachers. Thus it enhances inner faculty discussions concerning curriculum design and supports students in achieving the individually aspired profile of competences.

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